

DISORDERS OF COAGULATION AND HEMOSTASIS IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS AND VIRAL LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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Abstract:

Chronic liver diseases are a major global health concern, representing significant epidemiological, social, and clinical challenges. Among them, chronic hepatitis and viral liver cirrhosis are particularly prevalent and often lead to severe complications if left untreated. Hepatic injury disrupts the delicate balance of the hemostatic system, affecting coagulation, anticoagulation, and fibrinolysis pathways. This review summarizes current understanding of hemostatic alterations in chronic hepatitis and viral cirrhosis, their pathophysiological mechanisms, and clinical implications.

Significant advances have been made in understanding the etiology and pathogenesis of chronic hepatitis and liver cirrhosis over the last 30 years, which has facilitated the development and implementation of novel diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. The progression of chronic hepatitis occurs in multiple stages, depending on the activity of the process and the degree of liver fibrosis. Chronic hepatitis is a polyetiological disease, with primary etiological factors including hepatitis viruses, other infections, parasitic diseases, toxic-allergic agents, alcohol, gallbladder disorders, and others [2].

Hemostasis is a complex system in the human body, consisting of coagulation, anticoagulation, and fibrinolysis components. These components include plasma coagulation factors, cellular elements (mainly platelets), and the vascular endothelium. Normally, there is a balance among these components, preventing both excessive bleeding and unwanted thrombus formation [13].

It is well known that liver tissue damage affects the hemostatic system, as many coagulation factors, anticoagulant proteins, fibrinolytic factors, and thrombopoietin are synthesized in hepatocytes [10]. Liver injury leads to a marked impairment of coagulation factor synthesis, often associated with hypoproteinemia. The extent of liver damage correlates with the degree of protein synthesis, and parameters such as serum albumin, antithrombin III, thrombotest, prekallikrein, plasminogen, and alpha-2-antiplasmin may reflect residual hepatocyte mass [23]. Impaired hepatic protein synthesis is also one of the causes of liver failure [14].

In the early stages of liver platelet injury, platelet aggregation is increased. Although many studies have focused on hypocoagulation in liver cirrhosis, literature also reports normal or enhanced coagulation tendencies. Research shows that all patients with liver cirrhosis demonstrate thrombocytopenia and secondary coagulopathy, with prolonged prothrombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT), and international normalized ratio (INR). Nevertheless, blood hypercoagulability can occur despite prolonged PT, aPTT, and INR [17]. Tripoli and colleagues have shown that severe thrombocytopenia in patients with liver cirrhosis may reduce thrombin production.

In such cases, platelet transfusion or treatment with recombinant human thrombopoietin before surgery or during spontaneous bleeding can normalize thrombin generation [11].

The level of thrombopoietin in the blood depends on the residual liver mass. In acute liver disease, thrombopoietin levels may be normal or slightly elevated, whereas in chronic liver disease, plasma thrombopoietin concentration significantly decreases, representing a major mechanism of thrombocytopenia in cirrhosis. Additionally, hypersplenism in cirrhosis contributes to the reduction of platelet count [22].

Currently, the alterations in hemostasis and various forms of thrombocytopenia in chronic viral hepatitis are not fully understood, complicating disease management. In chronic liver disease, complex changes in the hemostatic system initially maintain a balance between procoagulant and anticoagulant forces, which may shift toward bleeding or thrombosis depending on various factors [1]. In the terminal stages of chronic diffuse liver disease, thrombotic processes often convert to hypocoagulation [12]. Regulatory changes in hemostasis, fibrinolysis, inhibition of anticoagulants, and reduced physiological plasminogen levels have been observed. Prolonged PT and thrombin time are characteristic of liver cirrhosis [3].

During decompensation of cirrhosis, synthesis of vitamin K-dependent coagulation factors (II, VII, IX, X) and primary anticoagulants (proteins C and S) decreases. Impaired synthesis of these factors is exacerbated by reduced intestinal absorption of vitamin K. Rarely, widespread hepatic necrosis can cause sharp reductions in procoagulant factors [20]. Soria J. and colleagues identified decreased fibrinogen levels and abnormal fibrinogen molecules in severe cirrhosis [11].

Severe impairment of liver function in almost all liver diseases may lead to coagulopathy and hemorrhagic diathesis. In patients with chronic viral hepatitis, hemorrhagic syndrome is associated with thrombocytopenia, coagulation abnormalities (prothrombin, fibrinogen), and increased tissue plasminogen activator activity [3]. HeX.F. (2004) demonstrated that prothrombin (factor II), a key coagulation protein synthesized in the liver with vitamin K, is decreased in liver disease, impairing thrombin generation [15].

The relationship between hemostatic parameters, inflammation, and liver fibrosis has been established. Increasing histological activity and fibrosis severity are accompanied by endothelial dysfunction, changes in coagulation indices, decreased platelet count, increased physiological anticoagulants, and altered plasminogen levels [3]. Research has also shown decreased C protein activity in patients with liver disease [15]. Standard coagulation tests, such as PT and aPTT, were developed not for in vivo hemostasis assessment but to monitor anticoagulant therapy [18].

In cirrhosis, fibrinolysis inhibitors are reduced, leading to enhanced fibrinolysis and potential hemorrhagic manifestations [9]. In patients with chronic viral liver pathology, assessment of fibrinolysis can involve measuring tissue plasminogen activator activity and plasminogen activator inhibitor levels [16]. Despite existing coagulopathies, literature reports increased blood coagulation in some cases of cirrhosis. Elevated factor VIII and von Willebrand factor, along with decreased proteins C, S, antithrombin III, and plasminogen, may predispose to thrombosis. Deficiency of these

factors, combined with increased consumption, activates thrombin formation even with low procoagulant levels [7]. Prelipcean C.C. and colleagues recommended anticoagulant therapy with heparin and vitamin K in cirrhosis-associated venous thrombosis, although bleeding complications remain high [21].

In patients with chronic liver diseases and cirrhosis, both hemorrhagic and thrombotic complications may occur simultaneously. Bleeding can be spontaneous, related to portal hypertension, or post-traumatic, and variceal bleeding does not always correlate with hypocoagulation. Thrombotic complications include portal vein thrombosis and venous thromboembolism, occurring in approximately 3.7% of patients [19].

Acute and chronic liver diseases predispose to intravascular coagulation syndromes. Hypercoagulability may result from tissue factor release from hepatocytes, impaired clearance of activated coagulation factors, defective synthesis of primary anticoagulants, and reduced blood flow in dilated portal veins, leading to thrombin formation, microvascular thrombus formation, and disseminated intravascular coagulation [6].

Overall, hemostatic disturbances in liver pathology are complex, multifactorial, and affect all components of the hemostatic system, often with unpredictable consequences. Complex and variable hemostatic changes in cirrhosis may result in diverse complications in patients with impaired liver function. Therefore, studying the hemostatic system in patients with chronic hepatitis and liver cirrhosis is clinically and scientifically justified.

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